

WASTE IS HARMFUL, IF IT IS RECYCLED IT IS A GREAT RESOURCE, A HUGE SOURCE OF ENERGY

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Abstract: The article evaluates the generation of municipal solid waste, its negative impact on human health and environmental sustainability. Changes in the morphological composition of solid household waste depend on the social environment of the local area, and the level of development of industry and agriculture. For example, the article shows Uzbekistan, in the summer and autumn months, the amount of food, cash crops, fruits and vegetables, and plant residues in the morphological composition of the MSW is high (60-70%).

Keywords: Municipal solid waste, environmental stability, deurbanization, waste management.

Today, not only in our country but also in the countries of the world, consistent work is being done to ensure environmental stability, deurbanization, environmental protection, public health, rational use of natural resources, and improvement of sanitary and ecological conditions [1].

It should be noted that food, paper, and polyethylene waste constitute the main component of the waste container in all countries of the world.

As a result of population growth, urbanization, expansion of consumption, and types of consumer products, the issue of municipal solid waste management, transportation, collection, disposal, disposal, and processing is gaining global importance.

Today, the problem of waste is becoming one of the most pressing environmental, social, economic, energy, housing, and communal problems not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the whole world, and the saddest thing is that this global problem has not been fully solved in any country of the world.

This problem is especially relevant for Uzbekistan, because the annual accumulation of all types of waste is very large, and the rate of their reuse does not exceed 30%. The direct impact of waste on people's lives and environmental stability is huge. Municipal solid waste (MSW) is collected directly at waste collection points around settlements, residential and recreational facilities, and objects of a social nature (Fig. 1) [3,4].

Figure 1. MSWs collection places (Karshi city).

In our country, 30% of waste is processed, and the rest is collected in landfills and buried.

As a result, as a result of the direct interaction with the environment, the temperature of the collected MSW in landfills rises to $45 \div 55^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the process of aerobic decomposition begins. At the same time, the upper layer of the waste pile dries up and easily ignites. Due to the high humidity ($85 \div 90\%$) and lack of oxygen in the waste layers, as a result of anaerobic decomposition of MSW, various compounds (NO , NO_2 , NH_4 , HCl , C , SO_2 , H_2S , CO , CoF_3 , AgF , ClF_5 , CH_4 , CH_3 , PhMe , C_2H_{10} , C_2H_{10}) spreads and leads to poisoning of the environment, depletion of the ozone layer and the formation of greenhouse gases. Thus, the problem of transportation, collection, neutralization, destruction, disposal and processing of MSW is urgent, first of all, in terms of their negative impact on the environment and human health. In addition, MSWs are a rich source of secondary energy resources and are cheap raw materials [5-10].

Any MSW consists of three components: organic and inorganic substances and water. Water represents the moisture content of natural resources, organic matter is considered an unconventional source of energy, and its study is of special interest today.

As the morphological composition of the MSWs changes, so does its heat of combustion. For example, in Uzbekistan, in the summer and autumn months, the amount of food, cash crops, fruits and vegetables, and plant residues in the morphological composition of the MF is high (60-70%).

The fuel, measures such as sorting of fuel into useful components, and sorting of metal and non-combustible parts are carried out.

As a result of the thermal processing of organic and polyethylene compounds that make up the chemical compounds according to their morphological composition, alternative fuels - pyro gas (heat of combustion $25\div 30$ MDj/m³) biogas (content of methane $50\div 70\%$, heat of combustion $22\div 24$ MDj/m³), pyrolysis tar (liquid fuel, combustion heat $25\div 30$ MDj/kg) and model houses, social facilities (kindergarten, school, buildings, hospitals, health care facilities) by receiving eco-briquettes, kitchens, and hotels), greenhouse farms, farm and field sheds, small industrial enterprises (brick kilns, mortar kilns, cement plants) with continuous and high-quality alternative fuel, equivalent to heat and electricity throughout the year supply of energy units, ultimately, the impact of waste on ecological stability will be eliminated, the destruction of fertile soils, the poisoning of underground water, and the emergence of various foreign diseases and virus foci will be prevented.

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